

Anatoma occidentalis n. sp. (Vetigastropoda, Anatomidae) from upper bathyal coral habitats off western Africa

Anatoma occidentalis n. sp. (Vetigastropoda, Anatomidae) de hábitats coralinos batiales superiores frente a África occidental

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ABSTRACT

A new species in the family Anatomidae J. H. McLean, 1989 (Gastropoda) is proposed: *Anatoma occidentalis* n. sp., found off Mauritania and Angola. Empty shells of the new species were found in sediment samples collected in habitats associated with deep-water corals from an upper bathyal depth range.

RESUMEN

Se propone una nueva especie en la familia Anatomidae J. H. McLean, 1989 (Gastropoda): *Anatoma occidentalis* n. sp., hallada frente a Mauritania y Angola. Se encontraron conchas vacías de la nueva especie en muestras de sedimentos recolectadas en hábitats asociados con corales de aguas profundas en un rango de profundidad del piso batial superior.

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KEY WORDS: Mollusca, Gastropoda, Atlantic Ocean.

PALABRAS CLAVE: Mollusca, Gastropoda, océano Atlántico.

INTRODUCTION

The Marine Research Department of Senckenberg am Meer (SaM) studies the geophysical, ecological and biodiversity aspects of deep-water coral (DWC) habitats in the Atlantic Ocean. Focus areas of this research are the DWC habitats off Mauritania (WESTPHAL 2007; WESTPHAL ET AL. 2014; RAMOS ET AL. 2017; WIENBERG ET AL. 2018) and Angola (HEBBELN ET AL. 2016, 2020).

This article is a contribution to the Mollusca in deep-water coral habitats; one new species is proposed in the genus *Anatoma* Woodward, 1859 (Gastropoda, Anatomidae McLean, 1989). GEIGER (2012) completed the most comprehensive monograph on the genus *Anatoma*. Species in *Anatoma* are found in all oceans on Earth from the littoral zones to abyssal depths. To date, 88

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species are known in *Anatoma* (MolluscaBase 2021) of which 20 species are known from the northern Atlantic Ocean, Gulf of Mexico, Caribbean Sea and Mediterranean Sea.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The samples studied herein were gathered during three expeditions by German research vessels to DWC habitats offshore Mauritania and Angola. In 2007, the RV Poseidon cruise POS346 concentrated on the southern coral mound chain off Mauritania (WESTPHAL 2007); sampling was conducted by box-cores. In 2010, the RV MS Merian cruise MSM16/3 sampled in and near DWC habitats on the coral mound chain as well as in canyons of the Mauritanian upper margin (WESTPHAL ET AL. 2014; RAMOS ET AL. 2017; WIENBERG ET AL. 2018); sampling was done by bottom grabs and box cores. In 2016, the RV Meteor cruise M122 sampled near DWC habitats off Angola (HEBBELN ET AL. 2016, 2020); sampling was done by bottom grabs and box cores.

The bottom sediments were sieved retaining fractions greater than 0.5 mm, and subsequently washed and dried on board. The sieved fractions were studied at SaM under low magnification binocular microscopes for molluscs. Selected specimens were prepared for imaging using a scanning electron microscope (SEM, VEGA3-Tescan); a gold coating was used to improve image quality. SEM imaging used an electron

incident energy of 10 KeV; micro-graphs were taken using both secondary electrons as well as back-scatter electrons.

The shells from Mauritania and Angola were compared with known species: literature records (GEIGER 2012; HOFFMAN ET AL. 2021) and samples in the reference collection at SaM.

The holotype and most paratypes are stored in Senckenberg Museum Frankfurt (SMF), few paratypes and other shells studied are retained in the reference collection at SaM.

The station numbering of the University of Bremen was adopted; its numbers can be traced back to various cruises and on-board station numbers. The station numbers are preceded by GeoB as in for example GeoB14910.

Coordinates have been converted to a decimal format to facilitate incorporation into maps and databases. The four decimals used suggest an areal accuracy of about 10 m; the actual areal accuracy of the location of box core is estimated to be 5 – 50 m.

Abbreviations:

Morphology

H: height of shell;

Ha: height of shell aperture;

W: width of shell;

Wp: maximum width of exposed protoconch.

Institutes

SaM: Senckenberg am Meer, Wilhelmshaven;

SMF: Senckenberg Museum Frankfurt.

Other

sta.: station.

RESULTS

Class GASTROPODA Cuvier 1798
Subclass VETIGASTROPODA Salvini-Plawen, 1980
Superfamily SCISSURELLOIDEA Gray, 1847
Family ANATOMIDAE J. H. McLean, 1989
Genus *Anatoma* Woodward, 1959

Type species *Anatoma crispata* (J. Fleming, 1828) by monotypy.

Anatoma occidentalis n. sp. (Figs. 1-8)

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Type locality: Mauritania, Tamxat Mounds; 17.5427°N, 16.6634°W; 510 m.

Type material (21 shells). *Holotype:* MAURITANIA • 1 shell (SEM sample, Fig. 6); Tamxat Mounds; 17.5427°N, 16.6634°W; 510 m; 15-Nov.-2010; sta. MSM16/3-GeoB14904; box core in coral rubble with silty mud; SMF359000 *Paratypes:* MAURITANIA • 4 shells (Figs. 4-5); same data as for holotype; SMF359001 • paratypes; 16 shells; data as for holotype; SMF359002.

Other material investigated (397 shells): MAURITANIA • 2 shells; Arguin Mud Wedge; 20.3651°N, 17.6634°W; 246 m; 24-Oct.-2010; sta. MSM16/3-GeoB14704; box core in muddy silt; SaM81238 • 3 shells; Tanôudêrt Canyon; 20.2450°N, 17.6689°W; 559 m; 3-Nov.-2010; sta. MSM16/3-GeoB14798; box core in fine sand; SaM78750 • 25 shells; Tanôudêrt Canyon; 20.2429°N, 17.6681°W; 490 m; 3-Nov.-2010; sta. MSM16/3-GeoB14799; box core in coral rubble with silty mud; SaM78750 • 3 shells; Tanôudêrt Canyon; 20.2458°N, 17.6698°W; 560 m; 3-Nov.-2010; sta. MSM16/3-GeoB14800; van Veen grab; SaM78751 • 9 shells; Arguin South 3 Canyon; 19.7381°N, 17.1465°W; 483 m; 7-Nov.-2010; sta. MSM16/3-GeoB14858; box core in coral rubble with silty mud; SaM81237. • 2 shells; Arguin South 3 Canyon; 19.7378°N, 17.1459°W; 493 m; 7-Nov.-2010; sta. MSM16/3-GeoB14860; bottom grab in silty mud; SaM81239 • 12 shells; Timiris Mounds; 18.9833°N, 16.8656°W; 482 m; 9-Jan.-2007; sta. POS346-GeoB11587; box core in coral rubble with mud; SaM78767. • 9 shells; Timiris Mounds; 18.9832°N, 16.8636°W; 474 m; 9-Jan.-2007; sta. POS346-GeoB11588; box core in coral rubble with mud; SaM78768. • 77 shells; Timiris Mounds; 18.9634°N, 16.8688°W; 498 m; 11-Nov.-2010; sta. MSM16/3-GeoB14877; box core in coral rubble with silty mud; SaM78753. • 2 shells (SEM sample, Figs. 1-2); Timiris Mounds; 18.9556°N, 16.8679°W; 493 m; 11-Nov.-2010; sta. MSM16/3-GeoB14878; box core in coral rubble with silty mud; gravity core; SaM78754, SMF359004 • 1 shell; Tioulit Canyon; 18.6479°N, 16.7249°W; 590 m; 13-Nov.-2010; sta. MSM16/3-GeoB14889; SaM78755 • 3 shells; Banda Mounds; 17.6459°N, 16.6665°W; 442 m; 7-Jan.-2007; sta. POS346-GeoB11564; box core in coral rubble with mud; SaM78761. • 2 shells; Banda Mounds; 17.6510°N, 16.6681°W; 441 m; 7-Jan.-2007; sta. POS346-GeoB11566; box core in coral rubble with mud; SaM78762. • 14 shells; Banda Mounds; 17.6643°N, 16.6726°W; 514 m; 8-Jan.-2007; sta. POS346-GeoB11568; box core in coral rubble with mud; SaM78763. • 6 shells; 17.6668°N, 16.6721°W; 440 m; 8-Jan.-2007; sta. POS346-GeoB11569; box core in coral rubble with mud; SaM78764. • 2 shells; Banda Mounds; 17.6752°N, 16.6700°W; 458 m; 8-Jan.-2007; sta. POS346-GeoB11578; box core in coral rubble with mud; SaM78765. • 36 shells; 17.6794°N, 16.6684°W; 450 m; 8-Jan.-2007; sta. POS346-GeoB11579; box core in coral rubble with mud; SaM78766. • 64 shells (3 shells SEM, Fig. 3); Banda Mounds; 17.7476°N, 16.6617°W; 414 m; 15-Nov.-2010; sta. MSM16/3-GeoB14903; box core in coral rubble with silty mud; SaM78756, SMF359005 • 22 shells; Banda Mounds; 17.5410°N, 16.6666°W; 486 m; 15-Nov.-2010; sta. MSM16/3-GeoB14905; box core in coral rubble with silty mud; SaM78758. • 67 shells; Banda Mounds; 17.8433°N, 16.6941°W; 535 m; 15-Nov.-2010; sta. MSM16/3-GeoB14910; box core in silty mud; SaM78759. • 23 shells; Banda Mounds; 17.4818°N, 16.6918°W; 450 m; 15-Nov.-2010; sta. MSM16/3-GeoB14911; box core in coral rubble with silty mud; SaM78760. ANGOLA • 6 shells (Figs. 7-8); Anna Ridge; 9.7447°S, 12.7816°E; 299 m; 1-Jan.-2016; sta. M122-GeoB20955; van Veen grab in coral rubble with silty mud; 2 shells (SEM) SMF359003, 2 shells SaM85666, 2 shells Naturalis, Leiden, the Netherlands.

Etymology: Latin adjective (*occidentis* - western); the name refers to the western African coastline where a significant number of shells have been found.

Description: Small shell with conical outline of spire with flattened apex; rounded whorls with selenizone; regular, fine but dominant axial sculpture; selenizone with regular and symmetrically-curved axial ribs; flexuous prosocline lip; umbilicate with distinct near-vertical umbilical keel (funiculus);

colour cream white; adult height 2.2 mm, width 2.5 mm.

Protoconch – flat paucispiral shell with 1 whorl (Figs. 2B, 3B, 4A, 6B); sculpture complex pattern of wiggly and branched short ridges, smoothly rounded on a smooth background, with faint spiral alignment above suture (Fig.

6b); lip curved with thickened rim, often partly broken; suture shallow impressed with last $\frac{1}{4}$ whorl of protoconch, protoconch-teleoconch limit deep; maximum width 0.19 mm.

Teleoconch – elevated spire with 2 $\frac{1}{2}$ whorls with deep suture (Fig. 1A, 2A, 3A, 4, 6A, 7A, 8A). Teleoconch 1 without selenizone $\frac{1}{2}$ to $\frac{3}{4}$ whorl with many regularly spaced, flexuous smooth axial riblets, without spiral cord in holotype (Fig. 6C), yet frequently with single spiral cord abutting on start selenizone (Figs. 2B, 3B, 5A). Teleoconch 2 with selenizone and spiral cordlets above and below selenizone. Distance between selenizone and suture below distinct and increasing gradually. Sculpture of shoulder with dominant, regularly spaced, rounded riblets, procline below the suture with overlying regularly spaced fine spiral cordlets; spiral cordlets absent on the swollen area below suture and on the protruding upper edge above the selenizone. On shoulder of body whorl about 90 axial riblets and about 18 spiral cordlets. Selenizone with evenly-curved axial riblets, well-rounded on smooth background; riblets at about same frequency as those on shoulder. Sculpture base whorls with

flexuous and dominant axial riblets and finer spiral cordlets forming a regular network of diamonds; frequency of axial riblets on the base similar to that on shoulder. Spiral cordlets absent on protrusions below the selenizone; axial ribs present. Deep umbilicus with reticulated sculpture up to sharp vertical keel (funiculus); area between keel and inner lip without axial or radial ribs but with numerous coarse growth lines (Figs. 1C, 3C). Vertical keel ends on lower columellar lip.

Aperture – nearly circular with slit at periphery, slightly above midline aperture, slit $\frac{1}{4}$ whorl deep with horizontally protruding upper edge and upward pointing lower edge. (Figs. 1A, 2A, 3A, 4, 6A). Parietal callus thin, lip distinct. Columella with straight vertical basis and rounded towards parietal area; lip sharp, narrow in upper half, wide at base at joint with funiculus. External lip thin, blunt, reclined at the base, flattened on the shoulder. Inside callus thin smooth with inconspicuous spiral imprint of selenizone. Aperture height 1.3 mm, 70% of total height.

Variability – Sculpture slightly variable in strength of riblets and cordlets; ca. 80 – 100 axial riblets on the body

(Right page) Figures 1-6. *Anatoma occidentalis* n. sp., from Mauritania. 1A: shell from MSM16/3-GeoB14878 (H 2.0 mm, W 2.4 mm); 1B: detail of the selenizone; 1C: detail of the umbilicus showing the funiculus; 2A, C: shell from the same locality (H 2.1 mm, W 2.4 mm); 2B: detail of the protoconch and first teleoconch whorl (Wp 0.19 mm); 2D: detail of the selenizone; 3A: shell from MSM16/3-GeoB14903 (H 2.1 mm, W 2.5 mm); 3B: detail of the protoconch and first teleoconch whorl (Wp 0.18 mm); 3C: detail of the umbilicus with funiculus; 4: paratype from MSM16/3-GeoB14904 (H 2.2 mm, W 2.5 mm); 5A: paratype, same locality, detail of the protoconch and first teleoconch whorl (Wp 0.19 mm); 5B: apical view (W 2.3 mm); 6A: holotype, shell from MSM16/3-GeoB14904 (H 1.9 mm, W 2.4 mm); 6B, C: detail of the protoconch and first teleoconch whorls of the holotype (Wp 0.20 mm).

(Página derecha) Figuras 1-6. *Anatoma occidentalis* n. sp., de Mauritania. 1A: concha de MSM16/3-GeoB14878 (alto 2,0 mm, ancho 2,4 mm); 1B: detalle de la selenizone; 1C: detalle del ombligo mostrando el funículo; 2A, C: concha de la misma localidad (H 2,1 mm, W 2,4 mm); 2B: detalle de la protoconcha y primera vuelta de la teleoconcha (Wp 0,19 mm); 2D: detalle de la selenizone; 3A: concha de MSM16/3-GeoB14903 (alto 2,1 mm, ancho 2,5 mm); 3B: detalle de la protoconcha y primera vuelta de la teleoconcha (Wp 0,18 mm); 3C: detalle del ombligo con el funículo; 4: paratipo de MSM16/3-GeoB14904 (alto 2,2 mm, ancho 2,5 mm); 5A: paratipo, misma localidad, detalle de la protoconcha y primera vuelta de la teleoconcha (Wp 0,19 mm); 5B: vista apical (ancho 2,3 mm); 6A: holotipo, concha de MSM16/3-GeoB14904 (alto 1,9 mm, ancho 2,4 mm); 6B, C: detalle de la protoconcha y primeras vueltas de la teleoconcha del holotipo (Wp 0,20 mm).

Figures 7, 8. *Anatoma occidentalis* n. sp. from Angola. 7A: shell from M122-GeoB20958 (H 2.3 mm, W 2.5 mm); 7B: detail of sculpture and selenizone; 7C: apical view; 8A: shell from same locality (H 1.7 mm, W 2.2 mm); 8B: umbilical area with funiculus; 8C: basal view.

Figuras 7, 8. Anatomia occidentalis n. sp. de Angola. 7A: concha de M122-GeoB20958 (alto 2,3 mm, ancho 2,5 mm); 7B: detalle de la escultura y selenizone; 7C: vista apical; 8A: concha de la misma localidad (H 1,7 mm, W 2,2 mm); 8B: área umbilical con funículo; 8C: vista basal.

whorl. Teleoconch 1 0.50 – 0.75 whorls; single radial cord may be distinct, inconspicuous or absent. Height to width ratio is lower in younger specimens. Occasionally, the umbilical slit is nearly closed. Adult height 1.9 – 2.3 mm, width 2.2 – 2.5 mm.

Distribution: Eastern Atlantic Ocean, Mauritania, Latitude 17.6 – 20.3°N, depth range 246 – 590 m and Angola, 9.7°S, depth 299 m.

Remarks: The radula and the soft parts of the new species are unknown. Only empty shells were found in or near coral debris with silty or muddy sand.

Differential diagnosis: The new species is similar to the NE Atlantic species *Anatoma crispata* and the W African *A. orbiculata*. Morphologically somewhat similar species are the NE Atlantic *Anatoma aspera*, *A. tenuisculpta*, *A. richardi* and the eastern and S African *A. agulhasensis* (Thiele, 1925). Other Atlantic species are clearly different.

Anatoma crispata is a common species on the continental slope off NW Europe (GEIGER, 2012: 832-847). Its outline is rounded; the initial sutsel is minimal, the axial ribs are strong and raised. The neotype figured by GEIGER (2012) has 62 ribs on the last whorl compared to ca. 90 in *occidentalis*. The new species has a distinct sutsel yielding a more stepped profile and finer axial riblets. Note that the size of the protoconch, the distinct funiculus and lack of umbilical sculpture is shared with *A. crispata*.

Anatoma orbiculata lives on the upper shelf off Morocco and Angola (GEIGER, 2012: 996-1000); *occidentalis* lives deeper. *Anatoma orbiculata* has a coarser sculpture with 46 raised ribs in the holotype versus 80 – 100 fine riblets in *occidentalis*. The spiral threads are also about twice as many, despite that they vanish near the suture on *occidentalis* and near the keel on *orbiculata*. Occasionally a funicu-

lus is visible in *orbiculata*, which leans towards the parietal margin; in *occidentalis* it is near-vertical and always distinct. The protoconch sculpture on *orbiculata* is coarser and shows spiral lines. The spiral lines on the shoulder of *orbiculata* extend to near the suture; in *occidentalis* they are absent near the suture.

Anatoma aspera is a common species on the continental slopes off NW Africa, western Europe and in the Mediterranean (GEIGER 2012: 774-788). It has a stepped and raised profile with a larger distance between suture and selenizone (sutsel). The selenizone is placed above the periphery. The axial sculpture on the shoulder is coarse. A funiculus is not visible. The new species has a more conical outline, a smaller sutsel, a selenizone slightly above the periphery, a fine axial sculpture on the shoulder and its funiculus is distinct.

Anatoma richardi is common in deep-water coral habitats on seamounts and island slopes near Madeira, Gulf of Cadiz, around the Iberian Peninsula, Azores and its adjacent seamounts (HOFFMAN ET AL. 2021: 141). The margins above and below the selenizone

are strongly protruding. A funiculus is not visible. The new species has smaller margins on the selenizone and a distinct funiculus.

Anatoma tenuisculpta lives on the shelf and upper bathyal in the Mediterranean and in the NE Atlantic from the Gulf of Cadiz to Norway (GEIGER 2012: 1109-1118); it is commonly found in deep-water coral habitats. The species has sloping (flattened) shoulders and a funiculus is not visible. The new species has more rounded shoulders and a clear funiculus.

Anatoma agulhasensis is predominantly known from the shelf and upper bathyal of South Africa and some isolated records off the eastern African coast; *occidentalis* lives deeper. A record from off Senegal needs confirmation. (GEIGER 2012: 744-751). Its outline is rather turreted and a funiculus leans towards the parietal area; the sculpture of teleoconch I has a strong spiral cord and ribs patterns. *Anatoma occidentalis* has a more compressed outline, a finer sculpture, a stronger indent in the upper columellar callus and a distinct near-vertical funiculus.

DISCUSSION

The new species has been found off Mauritania and off Angola; it has not been found off NW Morocco, the Canary Islands and the Azores or on seamounts in the Gulf of Cadiz and south of the Azores. The new species has also not been found in DWC habitats off central Namibia. It is most likely that its distribution is limited to the West African coastline from Mauritania to Angola.

The oxygen content of the seawater is lowered off Mauritania and off Angola and Namibia due to algal blooms at shallow depths; the decay of which results in oxygen minimum zones (OMZ) (WIENBERG ET AL. 2018;

HEBBELN ET AL. 2020). Shells of the new species suggest that the animal has lived recently in the OMZs possibly under more favourable conditions.

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BIBLIOGRAPHY

- GEIGER D.L. 2012. *Monograph of the little slit shells. Volume 2. Anatomidae, Larocheidae, Depressizonidae, Sutilizonidae, Temnocinclidae*. pp. 729-1291. Santa Barbara Museum of Natural History Monographs. Number 7.
- HEBBELN D., WIENBERG C., BENDER M., BERGMANN F., DEHNING K., DULLO W.-C., EICHSTÄDTER R., FLÖTER S., FREIWALD A., GORI A., HABERKERN J., HOFFMAN L., MENDES JOÃO F., LAVALLEYE M., LEYMANN T., MATSUYAMA K., MEYER-SCHACK B., MIENIS F., BERNARDO MOÇAMBIQUE I., NOWALD N., OREJAS SACO DEL VALLE C., RAMOS CORDOVA C., SATUROV D., SEITER C., TITSCHACK J., VITTORI V., WEFING A.-M., WILSENACK M., WINTERSTELLER P. 2016. ANNA, *Cold-Water Coral Ecosystems off Angola and Namibia, Cruise No. M122, December 30, 2015 - January 31, 2016, Walvis Bay (Namibia) - Walvis Bay (Namibia), Meteor-Berichte*. MARUM - Zentrum für Marine Umweltwissenschaften der Universität Bremen. 66 pp.
- HEBBELN D., WIENBERG C., DULLO W.C., FREIWALD A., MIENIS F., OREJAS C. & TITSCHACK J. 2020. Cold-water coral reefs thriving under hypoxia. *Coral Reefs*, 39: 853-859.
- HOFFMAN L., GOFAS S. & FREIWALD A. 2021. The genus *Anatoma* Woodward, 1859 (Gastropoda, Anatomidae) from Azorean seamounts. *Iberus*, 39 (2): 139-152.
- MOLLUSCABASE EDS. (2021). MolluscaBase. *Anatoma* Woodward, 1859. Accessed through: World Register of Marine Species at: <http://www.marinespecies.org/aphia.php?p=taxdetails&id=138464> on 2021-11-28.
- RAMOS A., SANZ J.L., RAMIL F., AGUDO L.M. & PRESAS-NAVARRO C. 2017. The giant cold-water coral mounds barrier off Mauritania. In Ramos A., Ramil F., Sanz J.L. (Eds): *Deep-sea ecosystems off Mauritania: Research of marine biodiversity and habitats in the Northwest African margin*: 481-525. Springer.
- WESTPHAL, H. (ed.) 2007. *MACUMA Integrating carbonates, siliciclastics and deep-water reefs for understanding a complex environment*. Poseidon 346 cruise report, Las Palmas – Las Palmas 28.12.2006–15.1.2007. 40 pp.
- WESTPHAL H., BEUCK L., BRAUN S., FREIWALD A., HANEUBUTH T., HETZINGER S., KLICPERA A., KUDRASS H., LANTZSCH H., LUNDÄLV T., VICENS G. M., PRETO N., VAN REUMONT J., SCHILLING S., TAVIANI M. & WIENBERG C. 2014. Phaeton – Paleooceanographic and paleo-climatic record on the Mauritanian Shelf – Cruise No. MSM16/3. October 13–November 20, 2010, Bremerhaven (Germany) – Mindelo (Cap Verde). *Maria S. Merian-Berichte*. 57 pp.
- WIENBERG C., TITSCHACK J., FREIWALD A., FRANK N., LUNDÄLV T., TAVIANI M., BEUCK L., SCHRÖDER-RITZRAU A., KRENGEL T. & HEBBELN D. 2018. The giant Mauritanian cold-water coral mound province: Oxygen control on coral mound formation. *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 185: 135-152.